

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This issue contains once more extended versions of papers that have received best paper awards at WebNet'98 (<http://www.aace.org/conf/webnet>), one of the major annual Web conferences.

We want to express our gratitude to AACE (<http://www.aace.org/>), the Association for Advancement of Computers in Education, for allowing us to contact award-winning authors, and to the authors concerned for their willingness to submit extended versions of their conference papers.

Hope you will enjoy the contributions!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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